

Past to Future

Towards fully paleo-informed future climate projections

Climate impact on past societies

Deliverable 20.1 | May 2026

University of Bern

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Funded by
the European Union**

OUTPUT SUMMARY	
Deliverable Name	Climate impact on past societies
Deliverable Number	D20.1
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package No	WP20
Lead Beneficiary	University of Bern
Author(s)	Nicholas Triozzi (UBERN), Caroline Heitz (UBERN)
Contributor(s)	Peter Ashwin (U. Exeter), Catherine Bradshaw (U. Exeter, MetOffice), Ignacio del Amo Blanco (UCPH), Isma Abdelkader Di Carlo (UU), Anneli Poska (TUT), Pir W. Hoebe (RUG), Hans Peeters (RUG), Stefanie Jacomet (external), Jörg Schibler (external)
Due Date (month)	February 2026 (original), 31 May 2026 (revised)
Delivery Date	28 May 2026
Abstract	This deliverable presents a multi-method Risk and Resilience framework designed to identify climate-driven vulnerabilities in Neolithic agropastoral societies of the Northern Alpine Foreland between 6.5 and 4.3 ka cal. BP. We introduce a replicator model that utilizes high-resolution downscaled climate simulations to analyze how environmental variability impacts the dynamic balance between different subsistence strategies. Finally, we specify the archaeological and paleoecological proxies required to evaluate these model predictions and establish a foundation for future research on human socioecological resilience.
Related Objective(s)	O1: Determine key processes and drivers of past climate changes including spatio-temporal variability and abrupt transitions as well as their impact on ecosystems and early societies. SO1.3: Understand the consequences of past transitions in (regional) hydroclimate on ecosystem variability (including extreme events) and impacts on past societies. O20.1: Develop a methodology to understand the climate and environmental factors influencing risk and resilience in ancient societies
Related Task(s)	T20.1 Develop a conceptual framework/model for the impact of climate on past societies (M1-12)

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of main changes
7 April 2026	1	Triozzi	First draft
14-19 May 2026	2, 3, 4	Triozzi, Ashwin, Bradshaw, Peeters, Hoebe, Del Amo Blanco	Contributions, figures and text
19 May 2026	5	Triozzi	Formatting, finalize text
20 May 2026	5 - final	Caroline Heitz, Hans Peeters	Final WP20 lead review
27 May	6	Stefanie Ypma, Anna von der Heydt	Final version for submission

Table of Contents

1. SUMMARY	3
2. EVIDENCE OF ACCOMPLISHMENT.....	4
2.1 <i>Introduction Background of the deliverable</i>	4
2.2 <i>Content of the deliverable</i>	7
2.2.1 The Model.....	7
2.2.2 Downscaled climate model data and its integration into the framework	9
2.2.3 Archaeological proxy data.....	15
2.2.4 Model testing.....	18
2.3 <i>Conclusion and possible impact</i>	19
2.4 <i>References</i>	19
3. DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION OF THE RESULTS	22
3.1 <i>Impact within the consortium</i>	22
3.2 <i>Impact within the wider scientific community</i>	22
3.3 <i>Impact beyond the scientific community</i>	24
3.4 <i>Future impact</i>	24
4. CHANGES WITH RESPECT TO THE DOA (DESCRIPTION OF ACTION).....	24

1. Summary

A conceptual and analytical framework bridging theoretical population ecology, human behavioral ecology, and ecosystems modeling was developed to assess qualitative and quantitative metrics for risk and resilience in past agropastoral economies. At the core of the framework, we are building a model based on a replicator equation. This is an evolutionary game theory approach to tracking changes in the relative frequencies of strategies present in a population of interacting agents. In the model, players employ one of three strategies (hunting, pastoralism, and farming). Interactions between players result in payoffs, which can be negative, positive, or neutral, depending on which two strategies are interacting and depending on the relative effects of climate or environment on the probabilistic outcomes of each strategy—our proxy for risk.

The model aims to predict the relative proportion of strategies employed in a population through time when the outcomes of strategies are constrained by climatic and environmental conditions, which we simulate using Trace21K-II climate model outputs from 6.5 to 4.3 ky cal. BP, downscaled to 10km spatial and monthly temporal resolution. We aggregate model predictions to reconstruct trends at annual and decadal scales to maximize compatibility with the highly resolved temporal resolution of archaeological proxies of human behavior recovered from Neolithic lakeshore settlements and sediment cores from lakes in the Northern Alpine forelands.

2. Evidence of accomplishment

The **primary objective of this deliverable** is to develop a conceptual and methodological framework for understanding **how past human societies respond to climatic and environmental variability**. This objective relates directly to Task 20.1: *to develop a methodology to understand the climate and environmental factors influencing risk and resilience in ancient societies*.

The central aim of this research is to explore the possibility of establishing interdependence between subsistence risk and resilience in human socioecological systems (SESs). We attempt to do this by operationalizing the terms “risk” and “resilience” in an analytical framework that will reveal vulnerabilities specific to the SES in focus. Our framework combines perspectives from resilience theory with behavioral models for risk-sensitive decision making into a hypothetico-deductive model. We tailor the model to be applicable to a particular type of socioecological system commonly observed in central Europe during the Neolithic (c. 6.5-4.3 kya cal. BP). Specifically, we apply this framework to understand quantitative aspects of economic diversities pertaining to pile-dwelling sites in the Northern Alpine Forelands. In doing so, we initialize our work on Tasks T20.2 and T20.3.

This deliverable has also fostered transdisciplinary collaboration within the P2F consortium and beyond. Contributing P2F members include Nicholas Triozzi [UBERN] (conceptualization, behavioral modeling, archaeological data synthesis), Peter Ashwin [U.Exeter] (conceptualization, behavioral modeling), Catherine Bradshaw [U.Exeter, MetOffice] (climate and crop yield modeling), Caroline Heitz [UBERN] (conceptualization, archaeological domain knowledge), Ignacio del Amo Blanco [UCPH] (behavioral modeling), Pir W. Hoebe [RUG] (climate modeling, archaeological data synthesis), Isma Abdelkader Di Carlo [UU] (climate modeling), and Anneli Poska [TUT] (palynological data). External collaborators, Prof. Stefanie Jacomet and Prof. Jörg Schibler of the Department of Environmental Sciences at Basel University contributed on-site archaeological data. This research was supervised by P2F members Caroline Heitz and Hans Peeters.

2.1 Introduction | Background of the deliverable

We refer to resilience as the degree to which a system can rebound, restructure, or reorganize itself to resemble its state before experiencing some perturbation. System resilience is therefore advantaged by its adaptive capacity, which can be expanded through innovation and learning (Carpenter et al. 2001). In addition, the diversity of responses available to a system experiencing a perturbation improves system resilience (Elmqvist et al. 2003). Studies that employ resilience in metaphorical terms (Heitz et al. 2021b,a) contribute to an illusion that a common, cross-disciplinary metric for resilience is elusive. However, if certain fundamental features of system resilience as defined above *can* be quantified (e.g., diversity measured by Hill numbers; Hill 1973), then resilience too is not only measurable, but can be demonstrated empirically. In our approach to measuring resilience we focus on response diversity because a

variety of strategies that are common across modern and prehistoric agricultural economies minimize risk through diversification (Marston 2011). To better appreciate how buffering risk contributes to system resilience, we explain how risk is operationalized in behavioral ecology.

Formal models in behavioral ecology provide an analytical framework for explaining adaptations to climatic and environmental variability. Such models typically predict the choices one *should* make under the assumption that immediate benefits of a particular behavior can be accurately evaluated relative to alternative actions (e.g., should I collect acorns while hunting for deer?). Fundamental features of such models are an alternative set of decisions, opportunity costs, a currency (e.g., kilocalories/hour), and an optimization goal. Together, these components are used to operationalize research about human behavior (Winterhalder and Kennett 2006) in a formal model that facilitates a quantitative approach to explaining the diversity of the human experience in terms of evolutionary theory (Coddington and Bird 2015; Smith and Winterhalder 1992).

Human behavioral ecologists have adapted more sophisticated models from studies on animal behavioral ecology that account for the real-world problem of variance in the outcomes of behavior (Winterhalder et al. 1999; Winterhalder and Golan 1997). While behavioral models focus on individuals, among social species like humans, information about the costs and pay-offs of decisions are transmitted within populations such that adaptations can accumulate into a body of adaptive knowledge that can endure environmental changes experienced across generations (Henrich and McElreath 2003). Scaling individual behaviors to the societal level is thus feasible and necessary to understand how human societies respond to and impact ecosystem stability.

Here, we operationalize risk as probabilistic variance in outcomes. This definition permits the study of how organisms (both human and non-human) perceive, prevent, and respond to variance and overcome uncertainty (Stephens 1990; Winterhalder et al. 1999). There are various ways to quantify risk (Tucker 2007) to identify behaviors that are risk-prone versus risk-averse. In agroecology research there are two broad approaches to risk minimization: diversification and intensification (Clark 1990; Halstead and O'Shea 1989; Marston 2011). Diversification strategies reduce variance by allocating time or energy across a broad array of subsistence activities. Agricultural examples include field scattering (Golan 1993; McCloskey 1991), poly-cropping (Jones and Halstead 1995), and transhumance (Kuznar 1991). Intensification reduces variance by increasing time and energy investments to achieve a surplus (i.e., overproduction) for example by applying manure to fields or constructing irrigation systems. These alternative approaches to reducing variance in agricultural production can have enduring impacts on landscape geomorphology (Neff 2008; Tianduowa et al. 2018) and species biodiversity (McClure 2013). Agricultural food production can also alter the isotopic compositions of plants (Bogaard et al. 2007; 2013), as well as human (van der Merwe and Vogel 1978) and non-human skeletal tissues (Triozi 2024), useful as archaeological proxies for reconstructing economic decisions in past human societies.

Archaeology is equipped with the methodological tools and theoretical frameworks for gaining **deep-time perspectives of human-environment interactions**. Formal behavioral models can be tuned to match the temporal resolution of available data. However, uncertainty increases as the temporal resolution of the model becomes more coarse. Advances in precision dating techniques, including accelerator mass

spectrometry (AMS) radiocarbon analysis and dendrochronology enhance our ability to evaluate impacts of climate and environmental variability on human socio-ecological systems (SESS) across multiple timescales. We therefore focused on archaeological data recovered from dendro-dated wetland sites in the northern Alpine Foreland with highly refined chronologies.

The Northern Alpine Foreland is home to hundreds of archaeological wetland sites situated in the littoral zones of freshwater lakes or in bogs (Figure 1) (Hafner et al. 2014). “Pile-dwellings” were constructed on timber supports driven into lake sediments during the Neolithic (c. 7.4-4.2 ky cal. BP), Bronze Age (c. 4.2-2.7 ky cal. BP), and Iron Age (c. 2.7-2.0 kya cal. BP). Anaerobic conditions of lake sediments are responsible for the exceptional preservation of timber supports and other organic materials including botanical remains (seeds, fruits, woods) and animal bone. Dendrochronological dating of timbers enables the delineation of construction, occupation, and abandonment phases as well as cultural and social transformations to be observed at sub-decadal to decadal resolution (Ebersbach et al. 2017). Some of the best-documented “pile-dwelling” sites occur in the Sutz-Lattrigen bay in Lake Biemme, Concise in western Lake Neuchâtel, Lake Constance, and Lake Zurich (Hafner et al. 2014). In combination with the rich “on-site” archaeological data obtained through excavations of pile-dwelling sites, we examine “off-site” archaeological proxies of human behavior obtained through paleoecological analyses of lake sediment cores from a selection of lakes in the study region.

In the following section, we discuss different components of the deliverable and how they integrate into a unified conceptual and analytical framework for risk and resilience.

Figure 1. Map of study area showing locations of a selection of wetland sites in Switzerland.

2.2 Content of the deliverable

This section is broken into four parts describing (1) the socioecological system model, (2) downscaling methods and modeling techniques applied to existing paleoclimate model data and how outputs are integrated into the modeling framework, (3) which on-site archaeological and off-site paleoecological proxies of human behavior have been assembled, and (4) how they will be used to test model predictions.

2.2.1 *The Model*

We model diachronic changes in human subsistence economies in the context of climatic and environmental variability in a replicator system. The replicator system (Hofbauer and Sigmund 1998; Maynard Smith 1978; Taylor and Jonker 1978; Zeeman 1980) is an idealized system that is a continuous time evolutionary game representing how individuals or group following mixtures of annual strategies interact, for example by trading, and how (on a short timescale) behavioral change and investment strategies or (on a longer timescale) differences in survival/reproductive success (i.e., fitness) lead to changes in these behavioral strategies. It can be derived from a generalized Lotka-Volterra system, but models only the proportions, not the absolute sizes of the populations.

We propose using this model to understand population changes over an annual timescale. It is typically used to understand biological or economic behavioral ecology (see Cressman and Tao 2014 for a review) but as far as we are aware, it has not been previously used in this context. It has the advantages of:

- a relatively small number of parameters (a payoff matrix for interactions between interacting agents, and a learning rate) to fit to proxy data of evidence of population mixtures;
- a clear interpretation in terms of relative proportions of populations following the strategies at any time; and
- a payoff matrix whose entries can be plausibly linked to climate data – for example droughts at different times of the year affecting pastoral or arable farming differentially, and hence the payoffs between these strategies.

We simulated a timeseries of changes in the relative proportions of three subsistence strategies: farming (F), pastoralism (P), and hunting (H). Changes in the frequencies of F, P, and H are interaction-dependent, and can be mutualistic, competitive, or asymmetric (i.e., one player benefits at the expense of another).

These three modes of production were practiced simultaneously and to varying degrees in terms of meeting calorie requirements by prehistoric agricultural societies for the past 10.5k years. Importantly, we do not presume agropastoral or complementary hunting-gathering strategies were homogenous across time and space. Different cultural groups developed unique combinations of specific farming, pastoral, and hunting strategies that were adapted to solve specific ecological problems. In addition, each mode of production may be understood as components of unique and sometimes interrelated systems subject to independent resilience metrics and vulnerabilities.

Nonetheless, we subsume all three systems and their unique properties into a single economic system for the sake of simplicity.

In our model we make certain assumptions about the sensitivity of players to risk in our parameterization of payoffs in matrix form. The payoff matrix characterizes the relative benefits of the interaction between actors following two strategies to the viability of each, considering how the interaction can reduce or increase variance around the expected mean energetic return rate. For example, we plan to use a z-score (e.g., Tucker et al. 2013) to characterize the annualized distributions of outcomes for two interacting strategies. z-scores are expected to fluctuate relative to the variable effects of climatic and environmental factors on the outcomes of each strategy. Thus, for any given year, a choice between two interacting strategies can be a risk-prone, a risk-averse, or a risk-neutral decision, depending on the z-scores.

This approach will allow us to test two non-competing hypotheses about the relationship between risk and resilience:

- H1) System resilience emerges when low-variance, risk-averse options consistently outperform high-variance, risk-prone alternatives. This hypothesis assumes that risk aversion contributes to a system's capacity to rebound to its former state following a perturbation.
- H2) A system's resilience capacity is enhanced by a strategic combination of attitudes towards risk. H2 assumes that risky decisions are necessary for a system to rebound.

If z-scores (with low values corresponding to low risk) are negatively correlated with the net benefit realized from the interaction between two strategies we might conclude that low-risk options confer greater fitness advantages than the alternatives. H1 would therefore be validated despite apparent fluctuations in the relative frequencies of each strategy in the population because the population tends to be risk averse. A lack of a correlation between z-scores and net benefits would then imply a variety of attitudes towards risk functions to enhance a system's resilience, thereby validating H2 and by extension, implicates diverse attitudes towards risk as a key contributor to resilience.

Results of two simulations of the dynamics of our replicator system in which climate is constant are illustrated in Figure 2. The initial (arbitrary) proportions of the population following hunting (H), pastoralism (P), and farming (F) strategies rapidly destabilize before settling at vastly different equilibria. In the left pane of Figure 2 the HPF-mixed state Evolutionary Stable Strategy (ESS) where all three populations are present emerges as the only observable ESS in the system (Figure 2). In the right pane of Figure 2, the frequencies of P and F collapse and only H survives. Note the sole difference between these simulations is the initial condition. On the left, the initial proportions of H, P, and F are 0.02, 0.9, and 0.08. On the right, these proportions are 0.03, 0.92, and 0.05, respectively. Trajectories are sensitive both to the initial state of the system and the net effect of two strategies interacting.

In the following sections we explain how we integrate climate and environmental variability into the replicator system.

Figure 2. A simulation of the replicator system with climate held constant showing (left) a balanced ratio of hunters:pastoralists:farmers is attained after an initial phase of variability (right) for the same parameters, but different initial ratios there is evolution towards a stable state with purely hunting strategies followed.

2.2.2 Downscaled climate model data and its integration into the framework

The Alpine region is characterized by complex mountainous topography, including steep elevational gradients, deeply incised valleys, and elevations ranging from approximately 200 m to over 4500 m above sea level. These landscape features give rise to strong spatial variability in temperature and precipitation across the region (Beniston and Stoffel 2014; Chamberlain et al. 2011). Accurately representing the influence of topography on climate is therefore essential when investigating environmental constraints on early agricultural systems in the Alpine foreland and surrounding lowlands.

The transient Holocene climate simulation used in this study was produced using a global climate model (GCM), that operates at a spatial resolution of 2–3.75° (~200–400 km at the equator). At these scales, Alpine relief is strongly smoothed, and key mesoscale climatic gradients such as orographic precipitation enhancement and elevation-dependent temperature patterns are poorly represented. As a result, direct use of raw GCM output is not suitable for applications that require spatially explicit climate forcing in mountainous regions.

To address this limitation, we use statistically downscaled climate data derived from the transient Holocene simulation TraCE-21ka version II (He et al. 2018; Liu et al. 2009). Climate variables were downscaled to a target spatial resolution of approximately 10 km using a hybrid physical–statistical framework informed by the CHELSA approach (Karger et al. 2017; 2023). This resolution provides a substantial refinement relative to the native GCM grids and captures the dominant mesoscale climatic structure relevant for agricultural productivity in Switzerland, while remaining consistent with the spatial scale at which archaeological patterns associated with the Neolithic transition are typically interpreted. Post-downscaling however, the temperatures for the northern Alpine Foreland remain systematically 5°C too cold because the coarse GCM cannot distinguish the low-lying Mittelland from the adjacent high Alpine terrain at its native resolution (Switzerland is covered by a single grid cell). A delta-method correction is therefore applied, adding the modelled past-to-present change signal to an ERA5-based modern baseline rather than using the raw downscaled values directly. Although

the Alps themselves display a notable dry bias, downscaled precipitation in the study region does not suffer from notable bias and so is used directly. The climatological means and timeseries are shown in Figure 3.

A reduced-complexity agro-climate model has been developed to simulate the climatic suitability and potential yield of crop functional types including winter and spring cereals analogous to early cultivated varieties of emmer wheat and einkorn by evaluating growing season length, temperature response, vernalization requirements, and water balance at monthly resolution. The model has been calibrated to the no-input and farmyard manure-input long-term experiments (1853-present) from the Broadbalk site in Hertfordshire, UK with crop functional type parameters appropriate for a historical-like pre-industrial wheat for the period 1853-1910 and a modern-like but input-limited wheat for the period post 1970. The intermediate years (1911-1969) are characterized by major structural changes (crop genetics, inputs and controls, and management regimes) so any variability in crop performance reflects climate variability combined with substantial and evolving shifts in the agricultural system making quantitative comparisons of the climate signal in this non-stationary system poorly constrained. Model performance is assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), calculated on standardized anomalies to focus on variability rather than absolute yield levels (Figure 4). The model reproduces a substantial fraction of the observed year-to-year variability, with correlations ranging from $r = 0.33$ to $r = 0.53$ indicating that a large component of interannual variability in yields can be explained by climate variability alone. The historical period exhibits lower correlations than the modern period, but these are still meaningful. The similar performance between the FYM and no-input cases indicates that, under historical conditions, the model skill is primarily constrained by the representation of climate-yield relationships rather than management inputs. This is consistent with the expectation that lower input systems are more directly coupled to climatic variability, although observational uncertainties in historical yield reconstructions may also contribute to the reduced correlations. In all cases, the model captures the sign and relative magnitude of many major anomalies, including both positive and negative extremes, although some discrepancies in amplitude and timing remain. Notably, the model tends to underestimate the most extreme negative anomalies and occasionally produces phase mismatches in individual years, highlighting limitations in representing compound stresses or localized impacts.

The consistency of skill across configurations supports the use of the model as a computationally efficient tool for large-scale or long-term assessments. Applied to the TraCE-21k-II downscaled climate reconstruction, the agro-climate model provides spatially explicit estimates of agropotential across the Swiss Northern Foreland through the Holocene, enabling assessment of how post-glacial warming, shifting precipitation seasonality, and interannual climate variability shaped the conditions under which early farming communities established and expanded in the study region. Figure 5 shows preliminary results from the model for three snapshot intervals during the study period for two crop functional types parameterised to reflect Holocene naked wheat and hulled cereals.

A full description of the downscaling methodology, bias correction, and application to crop-modelling experiments is provided in (Bradshaw forthcoming). Here, the resulting

climate and crop-model outputs are used as inputs to simulate climatic and environmental variation in the replicator system model. The downscaling methodology was used to produce monthly timeseries spanning 6.5 to 2.5 kya cal. BP for the following variables at 10km resolution covering the region of interest (Figure 1): mean, minimum, and maximum temperature, mean precipitation, solar radiation, thermal radiation, and mean windspeed. Each of these variables has strategy-specific effects on reward potential and collectively drive intra-annual variance in payoffs. The replicator system models behavior on a seasonal basis. Therefore, we aggregate climate variables for winter and summer (e.g., Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8).

Net primary productivity (NPP) was also downscaled to annual resolution but at a single grid cell for the sake of exploring potential impacts of an environmental force on the dynamics simulated by the replicator system model (Figure 9). In the simulation of NPP effects on strategy density the society seems to stabilize in a Pastoralist and Farmer society before collapsing to a Hunter only society by the action of the climate variable, which is the only forcing. Although the simulation employs arbitrary payoff effects, the results demonstrate how a relatively stable system can rapidly change states when payoffs are moderated by an external variable. We consider this to be a valuable outcome of our work which provides a compelling example of how tipping points can be modeled in human SESs. As a next step, we will use the downscaled precipitation and temperature data to model NPP directly using the Miami method (Zaks et al. 2007).

Figure 3. Mean temperature and precipitation over the study area from the downscaled GCM data for the modern reference period 1979-1999. a) Climatological mean, b) Timeseries for area mean over the study region.

Figure 4. Comparison of observed and modelled interannual wheat yield anomalies (standardized z-scores) for modern (1970–2014; top panels) and historical (1853–1910; bottom panels) periods under contrasting crop functional type assumptions. Left panels include farmyard manure (FYM), and right panels represent no-input conditions.

Figure 5. Snapshot simulated yields for ~2.5, 4.5 and 6.5 ka BP using the reduced complexity agro-climate model. Results shown are generated from the spatial mean of the downscaled climate inputs for the study region shown in Figure 3a.

Figure 6: Minimum, mean and maximum seasonal and annual temperature between 6500 and 2500 calBP at Burgässchsee. Downscaled TraCE21K-II data from centennial to monthly resolution.

Figure 7: Minimum, mean and maximum precipitation between 6500 and 2500 calBP at Burgässchisee. Downscaled TraCE21K-II data from centennial to monthly resolution.

Figure 8. January, July and Annual mean solar radiation between 6500 and 2500 calBP at Burgässchisee. Downscaled TraCE21K-II data from centennial to monthly resolution.

Figure 9. Results of a simulation of the replicator system (left) in which payoffs are moderated by average NPP normalized to the scale of payoffs (right).

2.2.3 Archaeological proxy data

Model performance will be assessed using on-site archaeological (e.g., faunal and botanical remains) and off-site (e.g., pollen) palaeoecological proxies for human subsistence activities. The on-site archaeological datasets are associated with

Neolithic lakeshore settlements (“pile-dwellings”) in the northern Alpine Foreland and include zooarchaeological and archaeobotanical data.

The zooarchaeological data consists of the number of individual specimens (NISP) observed for mammalian taxa. From these data, changes in the relative importance of key domesticated and wild species can be assessed (Schibler 2006). We focus on cattle (*Bos taurus*) and red deer (*Cervus elaphus*), the latter being interpreted as the most important hunted species contributing to Neolithic subsistence (Arbogast et al. 2006; Schibler 2006). Neolithic groups relied heavily on cattle husbandry for meat and dairy production (Bogaard 2004; Wright 2021). Changes in the relative proportions of cattle, non-cattle domesticates (e.g., sheep, goats, and pigs), red deer, and other wild species for different regions of the northern alpine forelands are visible in Figure 10.

Unlike the available zooarchaeological data, which enables generalized trends in the relative contributions of pastoralism versus hunting to overall subsistence, similar insights cannot be abstracted from archaeobotanical data. This issue is primarily due to uneven representation of key cultigens across excavated contexts. Problems of representation stem from inter-site differences in preservation of macrobotanicals and differences in sampling methods and research gaps. Lacking the ability to make 1:1 comparisons between observable contributions from farming relative to pastoralism and hunting, we turn to off-site palaeoecological land use proxies.

Agriculture results in profound environmental impacts that can be observed via paleoecological analysis of lake sediment cores. The presence of certain varieties of plant taxa known to have been cultivated by humans provide a clear signal of agricultural land use in the vicinity of lakes where pollen is deposited (Deza-Araujo et al. 2022). The depositional record of small lakes are particularly useful because smaller lakes have a more restricted catchment area than larger lakes. This means that small varved lakes such as Burgäschisee and Moossee in the northern Alpine Foreland, offer a more faithful palaeoecological record of nearby agricultural activities than larger lakes such as lake Constance (Hafner et al. 2020).

We aim to use agricultural land use probability (LUP) indexes (Deza-Araujo et al. 2022) calculated using palynological records from several small lakes in the study area (Figure 1; Rey et al. 2025). An example of the LUP index calculated using pollen data from sediment cores taken from three lakes in the northern Alpine Foreland is provided in Figure 11.

In addition to using the LUP to track the relative intensity of farming, we aim to work with palaeoecologists at the Institute for Plant Sciences at the University of Bern (IPS) to develop a workflow for isolating signals of animal husbandry in lake sediment records. Genera of fungi such as *Podospora*, *Sordaria*, and *Sporormiella* grow on animal dung and the abundance of spores in sedimentary records can serve as a coarse proxy for herbivore grazing intensity (Baker et al. 2016; Etienne et al. 2013). Local Pastoral Pollen Indicators (LPPI)—pollen taxa associated with livestock grazing (Mazier et al. 2009)—will also provide information about the extent of grazing by large-bodied herbivores in the lake catchment. Pairing the agricultural LUP with insights from LPPI-coprophilous fungi data would allow for estimates of the relative intensities of both subsistence modes to be tested against our model’s predictions.

Figure 10. Relative proportions of different mammal bones recovered from wetland sites dating to the Neolithic period in the northern alpine forelands.

Figure 11. Agricultural land use probability index calculated for three lakes in the northern Alpine Foreland with peaks corresponding to Neolithic and Early Bronze Age

periods where phases with wetland sites have been identified in the northern Alpine Foreland. Pollen analyses and LUP indices were published by Rey et al. (2025).

2.2.4 Model testing

In Section 2.2.1, we outline how a formal relationship between risk-sensitive adaptive tactics and system resilience could be evaluated in a modeling framework. Naturally, the next step is to assess the model's relevance for understanding resilience and vulnerability in past human societies.

The first challenge we face is that the model predicts *seasonal* changes in the relative proportions of the population hunting, farming, and herding (pastoralists). Despite the high precision chronologies obtained from preserved timbers at wetland sites, the temporal resolution of proxies for past subsistence strategies is much coarser and we cannot reliably reconstruct these behaviors at seasonal scales. We must therefore aggregate model predictions to the temporal resolution of the archaeological record.

The second obstacle is the model's oversimplification of subsistence decisions. H, P, and F are *extreme* generalizations of complex modes of productions that oftentimes entail interdependent scheduling of labor investments within the annual cycle—a dynamic we aim to simulate but may never fully replicate. While the hypotheses described in Section 2.2.1 pertain to attitudes towards risk, they do not address risk minimization strategies *per se*, leaving open the question of to what extent diversification versus intensification minimize climate and environment driven subsistence variability. However, we aim to pursue two viable and complementary approaches towards model validation.

The first method is intended to establish the accuracy of the model by comparing the simulation's predictions of H, P, and F frequencies against the metrics derived from on- and off-site data described in Section 2.2.3. Covariance will provide a useful and straightforward initial assessment of how well the archaeological data is predicted by the model.

We must go beyond this simple metric to explore diversification as a resilience strategy. Effective diversification is not merely spreading risk across a broader array of subsistence strategies; economists have argued that diversification is only effective in so far as returns from investments do not covary with the same external variable (Markowitz 1952; Tucker 2007). We will use a phase shift analysis to assess the relationship between our set of climatic variables and both the predicted and observed compositions of strategies in the population. This technique will be used to understand how readily changes to the frequency of each component of our modeled economy responds to variability. If diversification plays an important role in system resilience, we should not expect changes in the frequencies of the strategies to be in-phase with overlapping sets of climate variables. Instead, anti-covariation would be expected for any two strategies relative to fluctuations of some climate variable. If true, our framework will have demonstrated how minimizing risk through diversification enhances resilience.

2.3 Conclusion and possible impact

We formalize the relationship between risk and resilience by using an evolutionary game approach vis-à-vis the replicator equation. A particularly interesting feature is that the model includes the possibility of multiple evolutionary stable strategy (ESS) mixtures (i.e., bistability) for the same model parameters: there is not an inexorable evolution to a unique ESS but there can be multiple ESS (multiple “Nash equilibria” for the evolutionary game). This includes the possibility of stable H-only ESS simultaneously with a HPF-mixed state ESS where all three populations are present (see Figure 9). This raises the possibility of hysteresis (i.e., the dependence of the state of a system on its history) and irreversible tipping between ESS as climate variables are changed, and a potential cascade of tipping behaviors propagating from climate to human behaviors. We envisage that this will be a productive line of further investigation, as well as providing examples of potential future behavioral tipping downstream of earth system component tipping.

In addition, this methodology offers two important advantages that have the potential to make significant contributions to the field of anthropological archaeology and beyond. The first advantage relates to the model’s modularity. The interaction parameters themselves are based on our assumptions (i.e., biases) that all individuals are risk-averse. Hence, by tweaking the parameters, one can use the model to explore resilience of a socioecological system (SES) in which a range of attitudes towards risk are present in a population.

Secondly, the version of the model presented above is loosely based on Neolithic societies in central Europe. We track the three alternative subsistence strategies (hunting, farming, and pastoralism) known to sustain these types of human SESs. We are cognizant of the nuance within each mode of production and see great potential for exploring how other economic systems respond to climatic and environmental variability.

Moreover, the strategies we examine are deliberately broad for two reasons. First, we aim to use model predictions to generate hypotheses that can be tested empirically against the archaeological record that is by its very nature incomplete and imperfect. Second, we are drawn to the deductive power of simplified models. We do not presume model accuracy. On the contrary, the failure of the model to predict what we see archaeologically begs further scientific inquiry, which can be readily pursued by reflecting on our assumptions and adapting the model parameters accordingly.

2.4 References

- Arbogast, R.-M., Jacomet, S., Magny, M. and Schibler, J. (2006). The significance of climate fluctuations for lake level changes and shifts in subsistence economy during the late Neolithic (4300–2400 b.c.) in central Europe. *Veg. Hist. Archaeobot.* **15**: 403–418., DOI: 10.1007/s00334-006-0053-y.
- Baker, A. G., Cornelissen, P., Bhagwat, S. A., Vera, F. W. M. and Willis, K. J. (2016). Quantification of population sizes of large herbivores and their long-term functional role in ecosystems using dung fungal spores. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **7**: 1273–1281.
- Beniston, M. and Stoffel, M. (2014). Assessing the impacts of climatic change on mountain water resources. *Sci. Total Environ.* **493**: 1129–1137., DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.11.122.
- Bogaard, A. (2004). The nature of early farming in Central and South-east Europe. *Doc. Praehist.* **31**: 49–58., DOI: 10.4312/dp.31.4.
- Bogaard, A., Fraser, R., Heaton, T. H. E., Wallace, M., Vaiglova, P., Charles, M., Jones, G., Evershed, R. P.,

- Styring, A. K., Andersen, N. H., Arbogast, R. and Bartosiewicz, L. (2013). Crop manuring and intensive land management by Europe's first farmers. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **110**: 12589–12594., DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1305918110.
- Bogaard, A., Heaton, T. H. E., Poulton, P. and Merbach, I. (2007). The impact of manuring on nitrogen isotope ratios in cereals: archaeological implications for reconstruction of diet and crop management practices. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* **34**: 335–343., DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2006.04.009>.
- Bradshaw, C. (forthcoming). A global 10 km monthly palaeo-climate forcing dataset for impact modelling: downscaling, evaluation, and uncertainty. *TBC*.
- Carpenter, S., Walker, B., Anderies, J. M. and Abel, N. (2001). From Metaphor to Measurement: Resilience of What to What? *Ecosystems* **4**: 765–781., DOI: 10.1007/s10021-001-0045-9.
- Chamberlain, C. P., Poage, M. A., Craw, D. and Reynolds, R. C. (2011). Topographic development of the Southern Alps recorded by Cenozoic isotopic trends in river and lake waters. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* **123**: 38–55., DOI: 10.1130/B30094.1.
- Clark, C. W. (1990). Uncertainty in Economics. In E. A. Cashdan (ed.), *Risk and Uncertainty in Tribal and Peasant Economies*, Westview Press, Boulder, CO, pp.47–66.
- Codding, B. F. and Bird, D. W. (2015). Behavioral ecology and the future of archaeological science. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* **56**: 9–20., DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2015.02.027.
- Cressman, R. and Tao, Y. (2014). The replicator equation and other game dynamics. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **111**: 10810–10817., DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1400823111.
- Deza-Araujo, M., Morales-Molino, C., Conedera, M., Henne, P. D., Krebs, P., Hinz, M., Heitz, C., Hafner, A. and Tinner, W. (2022). A new indicator approach to reconstruct agricultural land use in Europe from sedimentary pollen assemblages. *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.* **599**: 111051., DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2022.111051>.
- Ebersbach, R., Doppler, T., Hofmann, D. and Whittle, A. (2017). No time out: Scaling material diversity and change in the Alpine foreland Neolithic. *J. Anthropol. Archaeol.* **45**: 1–14., DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2016.10.001>.
- Elmqvist, T., Folke, C., Nyström, M., Peterson, G., Bengtsson, J., Walker, B. and Norberg, J. (2003). Response diversity, ecosystem change, and resilience. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* **1**: 488–494., DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295\(2003\)001\[0488:RDECAR\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295(2003)001[0488:RDECAR]2.0.CO;2).
- Etienne, D., Wilhelm, B., Sabatier, P., Reyss, J.-L. and Arnaud, F. (2013). Influence of sample location and livestock numbers on Sporormiella concentrations and accumulation rates in surface sediments of Lake Allos, French Alps. *J. Paleolimnol.* **49**: 117–127.
- Goland, C. (1993). Agricultural Risk Management Through Diversity: Field Scattering in Cuyo Cuyo, Peru. *Cult. Agric.* 8–13., DOI: 10.1525/cag.1993.-.45-46.8.
- Hafner, A., Heitz, C. and Stapfer, R. (2014). Pile-Dwellings of the Neolithic and the Bronze Age in Switzerland. Long-Term Research and Future Tasks. In C. von Carnap-Bornheim (ed.), *Quo Vadis? Long-Term Research Projects in European Archaeology*, Wachholtz Verlag, Schleswig, pp.59–83.
- Hafner, A., Rey, F., Hostettler, M., Laabs, J., Bolliger, M., Brombacher, C., Francuz, J., Gobet, E., Häberle, S., Rentzel, P., Schäfer, M., Schibler, J., Wey, O. and Tinner, W. (2020). Archaeological and palaeoecological investigations at Burgäschisee (Swiss Plateau): new interdisciplinary insights in Neolithic settlement, land use and vegetation dynamics. In A. Hafner E. Dulbunova A. Mazurkevich E. Prankekaite and M. Hinz (eds.), *Settling Waterscapes in Europe: The Archaeology of Neolithic and Bronze Age Pile-Dwellings*, Bern and Heidelberg: Propylaeum, pp.173–204, DOI: 10.11588/propylaeum.714.
- Halstead, P. and O'Shea, J. (1989). Bad Year Economics.
- He, Feng. (2010) "Simulating Transient Climate Evolution of the Last deglaciation with CCSM3.", PhD Thesis University of Wisconsin-Madison.
- Heitz, C., Hinz, M., Laabs, J. and Hafner, A. (2021a). Mobility as resilience capacity in northern Alpine Neolithic settlement communities, DOI: 10.17863/CAM.79042.
- Heitz, C., Laabs, J., Hinz, M. and Hafner, A. (2021b). Collapse and Resilience in Prehistoric Archaeology: Questioning Concepts and Causalities in Models of Climate-Induced Societal Transformations. In P. Erdkamp J. G. Manning and K. Verboven (eds.), *Climate Change and Ancient Societies in Europe and the Near East*, Palgrave Macmillan, Cambridge, pp.127–199, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-81103-7_5.
- Henrich, J. and McElreath, R. (2003). The evolution of cultural evolution. *Evol. Anthropol. Issues, News*,

- Rev. **12**: 123–135., DOI: 10.1002/evan.10110.
- Hill, M. O. (1973). Diversity and Evenness: A Unifying Notation and Its Consequences. *Ecology* **54**: 427–432., DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1934352>.
- Hofbauer, J. and Sigmund, K. (1998). *Evolutionary games and population dynamics*, Cambridge university press.
- Jones, G. and Halstead, P. (1995). Maslins, Mixtures and Monocrops: on the Interpretation of Archaeobotanical Crop Samples of Heterogeneous Composition. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* **22**: 103–114.
- Karger, D. N., Conrad, O., Böhrer, J., Kawohl, T., Kreft, H., Soria-Auza, R. W., Zimmermann, N. E., Linder, H. P. and Kessler, M. (2017). Climatologies at High Resolution for the {E}arth's Land Surface Areas. *Sci. Data* **4**: 170122., DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2017.122.
- Karger, D. N., Schmatz, D. R., Dettling, G. and Zimmermann, N. E. (2023). High-Resolution Paleoclimate Simulations for the Last 21,000 Years Using the {CHELSA} Downscaling Framework. *Sci. Data* **10**: 1–14., DOI: 10.1038/s41597-023-02049-3.
- Kuznar, L. A. (1991). Transhumant Goat Pastoralism in the High Sierra of the South Central Andes: Human Responses to Environmental and Social Uncertainty. *Nomad. People.* 93–104.
- Liu, Z., Otto-Bliesner, B. L., He, F., Brady, E. C., Tomas, R., Clark, P. U., Carlson, A. E., Lynch-Stieglitz, J., Curry, W., Brook, E., Erickson, D., Jacob, R., Kutzbach, J., & Cheng, J. (2009). Transient simulation of last deglaciation with a new mechanism for Bolling-Allerod warming. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 325(5938), 310–314. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1171041>
- Markowitz, H. (1952). Portfolio Selection. *J. Finance* **7**: 77–91., DOI: 10.2307/2975974.
- Marston, J. M. (2011). Archaeological markers of agricultural risk management. *J. Anthropol. Archaeol.* **30**: 190–205., DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2011.01.002.
- Maynard Smith, J. (1978). Optimization Theory in Evolution. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* **9**: 31–56.
- Mazier, F., Galop, D., Gaillard, M.J., Rendu, C., Cugny, C., Legaz, A., Peyron, O. and Buttler, A. (2009). Multidisciplinary approach to reconstructing local pastoral activities: an example from the Pyrenean Mountains (Pays Basque). *The Holocene* **19**: 171–188., DOI: 10.1177/0959683608098956.
- McCloskey, D. N. (1991). The Prudent Peasant: New Findings on Open Fields. *J. Econ. Hist.* **51**: 343–355.
- McClure, S. B. (2013). Domesticated animals and biodiversity: Early agriculture at the gates of Europe and long-term ecological consequences. *Anthropocene* **4**: 57–68., DOI: 10.1016/j.ancene.2013.11.001.
- van der Merwe, N. J. and Vogel, J. C. (1978). 13C content of human collagen as a measure of prehistoric diet in woodland North America. *Nature* **276**: 815–816.
- Neff, L. T. (2008). A study of agricultural intensification: Ancient Maya agricultural terracing in the Xunantunich hinterland, Belize, Central America, University of Pennsylvania, Ann Arbor.
- Rey, F., Heiri, O., Wick, L., Gobet, E., Szidat, S., Leuzinger, U., Ebersbach, R., Hafner, A. and Tinner, W. (2025). Neolithic land use and forest dynamics on the Swiss Plateau (southwestern Central Europe). *Quat. Sci. Rev.* **360**: 109372., DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2025.109372>.
- Schibler, J. (2006). The economy and environment of the 4th and 3rd millennia BC in the northern Alpine foreland based on studies of animal bones. *Environ. Archaeol.* **11**: 49–64., DOI: 10.1179/174963106x97052.
- Smith, E. A. and Winterhalder, B. (1992). *Evolutionary Ecology and Human Behavior*, Aldine Pub. Co., New York.
- Stephens, D. W. (1990). Risk and Incomplete Information in Behavioral Ecology. In E. A. Cashdan (ed.), *Risk and Uncertainty in Tribal and Peasant Economies*, Westview Press, Boulder, CO, pp.19–46.
- Taylor, P. D. and Jonker, L. B. (1978). Evolutionary stable strategies and game dynamics. *Math. Biosci.* **40**: 145–156., DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564\(78\)90077-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564(78)90077-9).
- Tianduowa, Z., Woodson, K. C. and Ertsen, M. W. (2018). Reconstructing Ancient Hohokam Irrigation Systems in the Middle Gila River Valley, Arizona, United States of America. *Hum. Ecol.* **46**: 735–746., DOI: 10.1007/s10745-018-0023-x.
- Triozzi, N. P. (2024). Herding is Risky Business: Agropastoral Strategies in Neolithic Northern Dalmatia, University of California, Santa Barbara.
- Tucker, B. (2007). Perception of Interannual Covariation and Strategies for Risk Reduction among Mikea of Madagascar : Individual and Social Learning. *Hum. Nat.* **18**: 162–180., DOI: 10.1007/s12110-007-9007-z.
- Tucker, B., Tombo, J., Tsiazonera, Hajasoa, P., Nagnisaha, C., Lahitoka, V. R. and Zahatsy, C. (2013). Beyond Mean and Variance: Economic Risk Versus Perceived Risk of Farming, Foraging, and Fishing Activities in Southwestern Madagascar. *Hum. Ecol.* **41**: 393–407., DOI: 10.1007/s10745-013-9563-

2.

- Winterhalder, B. and Goland, C. (1997). An evolutionary ecology perspective on diet choice, risk, and plant domestication. In K. J. Gremillion (ed.), *People, Plants, and Landscapes: Studies in Paleoethnobotany*, University of Alabama Press, Tuscaloosa, pp.123–160.
- Winterhalder, B. and Kennett, D. J. (2006). Behavioral Ecology and the transition from hunting and gathering to agriculture. *Behav. Ecol. Transit. to Agric.* 1–21., DOI: 10.1093/beheco/art055.
- Winterhalder, B., Lu, F. and Tucker, B. (1999). Risk-Sensitive Adaptive Tactics : Models and Evidence from Subsistence Studies in Biology and Anthropology. *J. Archaeol. Res.* **7**: 301–348.
- Wright, E. (2021). Investigating cattle husbandry in the Swiss Late Neolithic using different scales of temporal precision: potential early evidence for deliberate livestock “improvement” in Europe. *Archaeol. Anthropol. Sci.* **13**: 36., DOI: 10.1007/s12520-020-01252-6.
- Zaks, D. P. M., Ramankutty, N., Barford, C. C. and Foley, J. A. (2007). From Miami to Madison: Investigating the relationship between climate and terrestrial net primary production. *Global Biogeochem. Cycles* **21**., DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006GB002705>.
- Zeeman, E. C. (1980). Population dynamics from game theory. *Global Theory of Dynamical Systems (Proc. Internat. Conf., Northwestern Univ., Evanston, Ill., 1979, Eds. Z. Nitecki and R. C. Robinson)*, Springer-Verlag, pp.471–497.

3. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of the results

3.1 Impact within the consortium

This deliverable will feed into a cross-workstream interdisciplinary workshop “*Connecting climate models with impact studies*” planned for September 2026. Presenting the content of our deliverable at the workshop will aim to summarize how our framework integrates climate model data into archaeological research. This will also be an opportunity to highlight some of the challenges we face in connecting palaeoclimate proxy data to patterns of human behavior observed in the archaeological record (in the report that is Deliverable 19.1 of “Past to Future”). Further, the workshop will foster avenues for advancing this research towards completing the work outlined in this and subsequent deliverables.

Additionally, this deliverable outlines an actionable workflow for completing Tasks 20.2 and 20.3, which focus on quantitative and qualitative (respectively) analyses of human responses to climate change events and the effects of variability on specific vulnerabilities and resilience strategies. For both tasks, we will apply our conceptual framework to address these issues using large, pan-regional datasets in addition to case studies from the northern alpine forelands. Continued collaboration with “hop-on” P2F experts in Eastern European prehistory and palaeoecology will provide important opportunities for expanding the regional scope of this work to the Bohemian-Moravian highlands and the East Baltic Coast.

3.2 Impact within the wider scientific community

This deliverable enhances knowledge within the wider scientific community by contributing better understanding of how human resilience capacities and specific vulnerabilities are connected to the ways in which individuals perceive and mitigate subsistence risk. The deliverable offers a novel analytical framework for studying human socioecological systems in the past, practical workflows for downscaling climate model data, and an innovative conceptual paradigm for human behavioral sciences.

These outcomes are directly relevant for:

- anthropological and archaeological researchers by introducing a new conceptual framework to be evaluated, scrutinized, and refined to the benefit of the field;
- paleoclimate modelers seeking an example of how to integrate their work into a transdisciplinary research paradigm that makes explicit links between climate dynamics and human-environment interactions; and
- economists interested in exploring how inter-cultural and inter-personal differences related to risk-sensitive decision making can have downstream, systemic implications across multiple social and economic scales.

This deliverable further strengthens the integration of population ecology and human behavioral ecology by (1) developing a formal relationship from otherwise abstract linkages between resilience, vulnerability, and risk; and (2) proposing viable approaches for using archaeological data to empirically evaluate these relationships.

Scientific Publications

<i>Title</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>Status (in prep, submitted, under review, accepted)</i>
A Population Model for Investigating Climate Impacts on the Neolithic Transition	Nicholas Triozzi, Peter Ashwin, Catherine Bradshaw, Ignacio del Amo Blanco, Isma Abdelkader di Carlo, Caroline Heitz		In prep
A global 10 km monthly palaeoclimate forcing dataset for impact modelling: downscaling, evaluation, and uncertainty	Catherine Bradshaw		In prep
Climate variability and the risk of agricultural failure in Holocene Switzerland	Catherine Bradshaw, Nicholas Triozzi, Hidir Serkendiz		In prep

Other output

<i>Type of activity (e.g. talk, poster, meeting etc.)</i>	<i>Details (where, who, what)</i>	<i>Target Audience + estimate on number of people reached</i>	<i>Impact Area</i>
Talk	Vienna EGU General Assembly; 4 May 2026, Vienna given by Triozzi	Scientific community (Approximately 50 climate modelers and proxy data specialists)	Strengthen research networks (Human behavioral ecology)
Talk	Research Colloquium of Prehistoric and Near Eastern Archaeology, Institute of	Future leaders and scientific community (Mix of 25 students,	Enhance scientific impact of P2F findings

	Archaeology, University of Bern, 12 May 2026, Triozzi	PhDs, PostDocs, and professors)	
Talk	European Association of Archaeologists 2026 Meeting in Athens; 26-29 August	Scientific community	Strengthen research networks
Poster	OCCR Swiss Climate Summer School, Grindelwald, 30 August - 4 September, Triozzi	Future leaders (70+ ECRs and climate researchers)	Strengthen research networks (Climate science and palaeoecology)

3.3 Impact beyond the scientific community

Understanding how human societies build resilience is crucial for ensuring that the well-being of future generations is protected from sudden and gradual climate changes. This deliverable uses the deep history of the ancient past as a "real-world laboratory" to identify the specific economic vulnerabilities of societies facing environmental instability. By demonstrating how ancient communities successfully balanced diverse survival strategies—such as farming and herding—to remain resilient, we provide policymakers and future leaders with a practical framework to evaluate social risk and long-term stability. Furthermore, this work improves climate literacy for the general public by showing that human resilience is not just an abstract idea, but a measurable capacity that can be strengthened to better prepare our modern world for a changing future climate.

3.4 Future impact

The outcomes of this deliverable are to be developed into a minimum of three scientific publications and presented by Triozzi (UBERN) in an oral presentation at the Annual Meeting for the European Association of Archaeologists in Athens (26-29 August) and a poster at the OCCR Swiss Climate Summer School in Grindelwald (30 August - 4 Sept).

We note that this deliverable provides important background that will underpin further work in WP20 and lead to Deliverables 20.2 and 20.3.

As mentioned in Section 3.1, the next step towards this will be a cross-workstream interdisciplinary workshop “*Connecting climate models with impact studies*” planned for September 2026. This will provide opportunities for exchanging ideas on how to strengthen the integration of climate model outputs and palaeoenvironmental proxy data into the methodological framework described here (in the report that is Deliverable 19.1 of “Past to Future”). We expect the workshop will serve to extend the current interdisciplinary team of P2F members by onboarding palaeoecological proxy specialists with the aim of completing the work outlined in this deliverable.

4. Changes with respect to the DoA (Description of Action)

The original due date of D20.1 has been changed from Month 12 to Month 15 as progress has been hampered by unplanned unavailability of involved staff. The progress

of this deliverable has been coordinated primarily by Triozzi (UBERN) and Ashwin (U.Exeter). The following actions have been taken to ensure the related tasks are done as stated in the DoA:

- Following the General Assembly #1, Triozzi assembled a multidisciplinary team of eight P2F ECRs and senior researchers to collaborate on Task 20.1 towards completion of Deliverable 20.1.
- The development of the behavioural model was finalized by end of March 2026. This was followed by synthesizing the other components of the model, including crop yield simulations, carrying capacity, and the archaeological data.

Only WP5 in WS1 relies on outputs of WP20 in WS4 (see Figure 2, Annex 1: 101184070-P2F- Part B- Page 10) but the leader of WP5 (Lunt [U.Bristol]) does not foresee any impact of the delay.